

In Vitro Study of a Novel Biofunctionalization for 3D PDMS Scaffold Via Surface Modification

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Introduction and Experimental

Three dimensional scaffold effect by electrospinning

- Body cells are embedded in the extracellular matrix (ECM), a **three-dimensional** (3D) complex constituted by fibrous proteins and molecules.
- Nanofibers have a similar shape to the natural **ECM**, which is characterized by continuous fibrous, high porosity, varying pore size, and large specific surface area.

Polydimethylsiloxane

Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is the most widely used silicon-based organic polymer, and is particularly

Properties : non-toxicity, flexible, transparency, biocompatibility, chemical inertness

Application : microfluidic devices, sensors, biomedical products, separation

Experimental

Electrospinning condition	
Voltage	7~9kV
Distance	15cm
Temperature	100°C
Flow rate	Core) 0.5mL/h Shell) 2.4mL/h

Scheme 1. Schematic PDMS nanosheets scaffold by electrospinning.

Scheme 2. Schematic procedure for the modification of the PDMS surface.

Measurement of Morphology

Figure 1. OM images of PDMS@PVP nanofibers (a), (b), PDMS nanofibers (c), (d), and TEM images of PDMS@PVP core-shell nanofiber (e), (f).

Figure 2. FE-SEM images of PDMS@PVP core-shell nanosheets (a), (b), dissolving PVP nanosheets (i), (j) and oxygen plasma PDMS nanosheets (k), (l).

Physicochemical property

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 3. FT-IR spectra of electrospun fibrous sheet (a) PDMS@PVP core-shell nanosheets, (b) After dissolving PVP, PDMS nanosheets, (c) Oxygen plasma PDMS nanosheets.

Figure 4. TGA curves of electrospun fibrous sheet : (a) PDMS@PVP core-shell nanosheets (b) After dissolving PVP, PDMS nanosheets (c) Oxygen plasma PDMS nanosheets.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curve of PDMS@PVP core-shell nanosheets (a), plasma PDMS nanosheets (b), PDMS nanosheets (c).

Cell culture

Figure 6. Fluorescence microscope image of HepG2, AML12 cells culture at 5day. (a)-(c) HepG2 cell line, (d)-(f) AML12 cell line, (a),(d) PDMS matrix scaffold, (b),(e) PDMS nanosheets scaffold, (c),(f) Plasma PDMS nanosheets scaffold.

Conclusion

In conclusion, PDMS nanosheets have been prepared successfully by core-shell electrospinning of a liquid PDMS precursor and a thermoplastic sheath, in situ curing treatment of the PDMS core, and dissolving off the sheath layer.

Nanofibers have a similar shape to the natural ECM, which is characterized by continuous fibrous, high porosity, varying pore size, and large specific surface area. The three-dimensional scaffold has a larger surface area, the cell-cell interaction and cell-substrate interaction than the two-dimensional scaffold. The result PDMS nanosheets were evaluated as substrates for scaffold. Compared to surface modified PDMS nanosheets with a biocompatible material and non-surface modified PDMS nanosheets, cell adhesion and proliferation were more efficient on surface modified PDMS nanosheets.

References

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